

Current Trends in the Treatment of Hepatocellular Carcinoma: Clinical Applications and Advancement

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ABSTRACT

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The fifth most common malignancy in humans is hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), or liver cancer. Also the most fatal kind of the disease. Increased liver cancer cases threaten world health. Predictions show around one million people will get liver cancer by 2025. Hepatocellular carcinoma accounts for 90% of liver cancer. Globally, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) ranks third in death and sixth in incidence. Both B and C hepatitis increase cirrhosis risk. Alcohol intake is five times more risky than hepatitis C. Advanced age, male gender, hepatitis D, and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis are risk factors. The multi-stage HCC pathophysiology is complex. Early hepatocyte malignant transformation and HCC development are caused by multiple causes. To validate the diagnosis, no pathology evidence is required. Various radiologic exams, including as ultrasounds, CT scans, and MRIs, can be conducted as part of a screening. The sole options for treatment that ensure a complete recovery are orthotopic liver transplantation (OLT) or surgical removal. Additional treatments include cryoablation, molecularly targeted medicines, systemic chemotherapy, and radiotherapy. The treatment is determined by the tumor's size, location, other organ damage, and liver function at the beginning. Cirrhosis is a common progression stage for HCC. Prompt antiviral treatment, safe injection practices, hepatitis B immunisation, treatment and education for intravenous drug users and alcoholics, and universal blood product screening can all help prevent hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

Graphical Abstract:

1. Introduction

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), the fifth most common malignancy worldwide, kills the most people. [1] HCC is eighth in US cancer rankings. 2013, 30,640 persons were diagnosed with liver and intrahepatic bile duct cancer, 21,670 of them died [2]. HCC was most common in Melanesia, Micronesia/Polynesia, Eastern and Southern Asia, and Middle and Western Africa, with men 2.4 times more prevalent than women. American Indians and Alaska Natives have the highest age-adjusted liver cancer incidence rates, increasing from 1.6 per 100,000 to 4.6 per 100,000 [3]. Blacks, Whites, and Hispanics follow closely after. As hepatitis C develops and obesity and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) increase in prevalence in the United States, certain ethnic groups will see a continued increase in HCC [4]. A combination of hereditary and environmental factors leads to HCC [5]. Liver cirrhosis, hepatitis B or C infection, severe alcohol use, aflatoxin B1 exposure, and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis are hepatocellular carcinoma risk factors. Disease stage affects cancer survival [6].

Liver cancer is a global health issue due to its rising prevalence. We expect about one million new liver cancer cases per year by 2025. Roughly 90% of liver cancer cases are HCC[7]. About 50% of all hepatocellular cancer cases are caused by HBV infection. Achieving sustained virological response (SVR) with antiviral medication has

greatly reduced HCV infection risk [8]. Even after HCV eradication, cirrhosis patients are more likely to develop HCC.

Aristolochic acid and tobacco use have both been linked to HCC through analyses of mutational signatures[9]. Each every case of HCC has its own unique molecular pathogenesis due to the unique genotoxic insults and underlying causes. Despite advances in our knowledge of the disease's biology and the factors that contribute to its development, these insights have not yet been applied in clinical practise [10].

2. Epidemiology

In terms of incidence, HCC ranks sixth worldwide, while its fatality rate places it third. The highest rates of occurrence are found in Southeast Asian countries and in China and the countries bordering on Sub-Saharan Africa [11]. Globally, HCC is the sixth most common and third most lethal malignancy. [12]. The US has seen less viral hepatitis cases since 2011 [13]. Prevention may explain this pattern. Even low-incidence areas saw case increases of around 20% from 1990 to 2015. The most frequent liver disease in China is hepatitis B. Alcoholism kills most people in sub-Saharan Africa, Europe, and Southeast Asia (see [14]). In Japan, Australia, and New Zealand, hepatitis C is the major cause of liver cancer, as it is in the Middle East and North Africa. NAFLD is a prominent cause of colorectal carcinoma (HCC) worldwide, but it is over 20%

prevalent in the Americas and Oceania (Figure 1). Alcohol-related liver illnesses (30%), nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (16%), hepatitis B (33%), and C (21%). Asia accounts for 72.5% of cases, Europe 9.7%, Africa 7.8%, North America 5.1%, and Latin America and the Caribbean 4.4% [17].

Figure 1 Schematic representation of non-alcoholic fatty liver

3. Risk Factors

Nearly 90% of HCC cases are linked to chronic liver disease. Cirrhosis is the sole major HCC risk factor, regardless of source. A clinician sees one to six new HCC cases in cirrhotic adults each year [18]. Many risk factors have been linked to HCC. Chronic alcoholism, diabetes or obesity-related non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), and HBV/HCV infection are examples. HCC risk factors include hemochromatosis, alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency, and primary biliary cholangitis-induced cirrhosis [19].

Hepatitis B virus infection :- The hepatitis B virus causes 60% of HCC cases in Asia and Africa and 20% in the West [20]. HBV can activate oncogenes by inserting itself into the host genome and causing insertional mutagenesis [21]. HBV increases the risk of HCC even though most patients with HBV-induced HCC have cirrhosis [22].

Hepatitis C virus infection:- Liver cancer patients in the Western Hemisphere often have chronic hepatitis C virus infection. Cirrhosis and chronic liver injury with bridging fibrosis are the only conditions that increase HCC risk due to HCV's genomic integration [23]. Direct-acting

antiviral (DAA) treatment has increased the number of HCV-infected people who have achieved SVR, reducing HCC risk by 50–80% [24].

Hepatitis D virus infection:- HBV surface antigens are necessary for HDV replication and infection[25]. This is because HDV is RNA. Twenty to forty million have HDV[26]. HDV infection increases liver disease severity, including fibrosis and cirrhosis, compared to HBV infection alone.

Alcohol:- Cancer can result from heavy alcohol use, including cirrhosis, HCC, and alcoholic liver disease. Cirrhosis from nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) and prolonged alcohol use has increased (Figure 2). Alcohol-related cirrhosis accounts for 15-30% of all HCC cases worldwide [27]. Population-based studies had 1% annual incidence rates, while tertiary care referral centres had 2-3% [27]. Some study suggests that HBV carriers who drink alcohol are more likely to develop HCC [28]. Heavy alcohol usage can induce hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) for many reasons.

NASH :- People with diabetes or obesity often develop NASH, which can lead to HCC [29]. This makes NASH a common etiological cause of cirrhosis in humans. The rising incidence of obesity has caused nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) to surpass alcoholic liver disease as the leading cause of cirrhosis globally. There has been a disturbing correlation between NASH and a large number of HCC cases since 2010; currently, 15–20% of HCC diagnoses in the West are due to NASH[30]. Furthermore, because it occurs in conjunction with other liver diseases, the population attributable proportion of metabolic syndrome and NASH is anticipated to be greater than 20% [31].

Age, sex & other factors:- HCC risk is linked to demographic characteristics, especially in cirrhotic patients. The largest age-specific incidence is in persons over 70[32], making ageing a major risk factor. Men get HCC approximately twice as often as women. Hormonal differences between the sexes and the fact that risk factors are more common in men likely account for this discrepancy [33]. The current evidence suggests that HCC affects Hispanics at a higher rate than other ethnic groups. This contrast may be explicable by the elevated frequency of PNPLA3 single-nucleotide mutations associated with NASH [34]. Tobacco use is linked to an increased incidence of HCC, according to epidemiological research. We still don't know, outside of studies, how food contributes to lowering HCC risk.

transplantation, which are based on their groundbreaking work. Cinquanta patients were enrolled in the trial.

6. Non surgical approaches

Trans arterial chemoembolization:- In addition to being utilised to downstage tumours that do not fulfil the inclusion/exclusion criteria, TACE is frequently utilised as a first-line treatment for locoregional HCC. 122 If the primary tumour has grown too large, or if micrometastases have spread from the original site, neoadjuvant therapy with TACE before HR and RFA may be an option to explore [46]. Transaminoethanol embolisation is used because HCC is neoangiogenic and the tumor's hepatic artery supply is targeted. Initial tumour blood supply comes from the portal system [47].

Transarterial radiation:- Microspheres filled with radioisotopes are introduced to the tumour by a catheter in transarterial radioembolization, an internal radiation treatment method. It is quite similar to transarterial chemoembolization (TACE) in that the patient is injected with Yttrium-90 (Y-90) microspheres or iodine-131-labeled lipiodol127. Patients with cirrhosis and HCC have benefited from this approach, and it has been associated with safe and successful outcomes [49]. While Y-90 serves as a signal, TACE has always been viewed as a contraindication when it comes to portal vein neoplastic thrombosis [50]. People are usually able to deal with the unfavourable consequences. The most commonly reported side effects are feeling tired all the time, throwing up, and experiencing stomach pain [51].

Percutaneous local ablation:- The gold standard for HCC in BCLC stages 0-A that is not surgically treatable is percutaneous local ablation, which can be achieved with radiofrequency ablation (RFA) or percutaneous ethanol injection (PEI) [52]. For localised liver tumour eradication, radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is the gold standard. Radiative coagulative necrosis of the tumour (RBA) is the most prevalent kind of local ablative therapy, and it leaves a perimeter of normal tissue surrounding the cancer unharmed [53].

Microwave ablation:- A potentially curative ablative treatment, microwave ablation (MWA) can be administered percutaneously or during surgery. 137. While radiofrequency ablation (RFA) and this method are quite similar, the latter uses radio waves to irradiate and ablate tumour foci, while the former uses electromagnetic waves with frequencies more than 900 kilohertz [54].

Figure 2 Risk factors causing liver cirrhosis

4. Mechanism & pathophysiology

Complex multi-stage HCC pathophysiology. Hepatocyte malignant transformation and HCC start with several complex factors [36]. Hereditary, viral-nonviral risk factor interactions, cellular environment, immune cells, and chronic liver disease severity all play a role [37]. From transformation to invasion and metastasis, a changed microenvironment affects cancer development [38]. In the first part of this primer series, we reviewed HCC's primary oncogenic drivers and signalling pathways [39].

5. Surgical approaches

Resection:- With a 5-year survival rate of 41%-74%, surgical resection is considered by most clinicians treating noncirrhotic patients as having the best curative rate [42]. The gold standard for the care of HCC has been laparoscopic liver resection, which is less intrusive and more effective in cirrhotic patients than open surgery. For more advanced cancers, resection is frequently the main therapy option until a liver transplant can be arranged[43]. range from 108 to 111 Laparoscopic resection would replace the more invasive open technique if it were theoretically feasible. Various criteria have been investigated to aid in the selection of suitable surgical candidates, including tumour size and location and liver function [44].

Liver transplant- Orthotopic liver transplantation (OLT), the only option for treating solid malignancies, is the best cure for decompensated cirrhosis. Mazzaferro et al.113 published the Milan criteria[45] for HCC

7. Drugs used for HCC mechanism

8. Patients with severe disease or whose disease had progressed to an advanced stage despite prior treatment attempts had a poor prognosis prior to 2007[56]. Among the 57 systemic drugs authorised by the FDA between 2007 and 2016 for the treatment of advanced HCC, only sorafenib is listed in Table 1. Due to quick progress in the field, numerous immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) and molecularly targeted drugs have been authorised as treatments for advanced HCC in the last three years [58]. Recent decades have seen remarkable progress in molecular cell biology's comprehension of tumorigenesis and its progression, which has allowed for the creation of innovative molecular targeted agents that inhibit underlying molecular abnormalities as successful cancer treatments [59].

Table 1 Trials of molecular targeted treatment for advanced hepatocellular carcinoma

Drugs	Name /ID	Phase	Target	Status
Sorafenib	SHARP	III	Multikinase	First-line,2008
Lenvatinib	REFLECT	II	Multikinase	First-line,2018
Erlotinib	SEARCH	III	EGFR	/
Tinivatinib	NCT01755767	III	cMET	/
Ramucrimab	REACH-2	III	VEGFR2	Second-line,2019
Roblifenib	NCT023255739	I/II	FGFR4	/
Liniifganib	NCT01009593	III	VEGFR,PDGFR	/

Table 1. Phase III studies of new medications for non-alcoholic steatohepatitis

Mechanism of action	Drug	Main Endpoint	Clinical trial	Expected Completion date
PPAR/Agonist	Elafibranor	NASH resolution without fibrosis worsening	RESOLUTION	December 2021
ASK1 inhibitor	Selonsferbit	>1 fibrosis stage improvement.	STELLAR4	January 2020
FXR agonist	Obeticholic acid	Composite endpoint: improvement in >1 stage fibrosis NASH resolution without deterioration.	REGENERATE	October 2021
CCR2/5	Cenicriviroc	Improvement in >1 fibrosis stage and no NASH worsening	AURORA	July 2019

7.4 Cabozantinib

A tiny pharmacologic kinase inhibitor known as cabozantinib inhibits the activity of several enzymes, including MET, VEGFR 1-3, RET, KIT, AXL, and FLT3

Everolimus	EVOLVE-1	III	mTOR	/
Apatinib	AHELP	III		

7.1 Sorafenib

Oral targeted kinase inhibitor sorafenib (TKI) reduces tumour growth and angiogenesis, which play a role in HCC [60] (Table 2). By blocking VEGFRs 1-3, PDGFRs, and Raf-MEK-ERK signalling pathways, the process is completed. ASCO 2007's SHARP (Sorafenib Hepatocellular Carcinoma Assessment Randomised Protocol; NCT00105443) trial found sorafenib effective against HCC [61].

7.2 Lenvatinib

Lenvatinib Initial treatment with additional medications in Phase III trials did not increase survival compared to placebo or sorafenib [62]. Lenvatinib, an orally available small-molecule inhibitor of RET, platelet-derived growth factor receptor kinase, and VEGF receptors 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. Lenvatinib targets the FGF signalling pathway, unlike sorafenib, to treat HCC.

7.3 Regorafenib

The oral kinase inhibitor regorafenib inhibits a number of proteins, including retinoic acid-related tyrosine kinase 2 (TIE2), c-KIT, PDGFR, FGFR1, RET, and RET-related tyrosine kinase [64]. Tsai and Lee's preclinical research showed that anti-TIE2 and sorafenib increased overall survival in a melanoma mouse, suggesting that regorafenib's combined blocking of the VEGFR2 and TIE2 pathways may have a broader antiangiogenic effect [65].

[66]. One reason cabozantinib is so effective against HCC is that it inhibits both MET and VEGFR2 [67].

7.5 Ramucirumab

In phase II studies, patients with advanced HCC were found to have a reduction in tumour growth and an inhibition of the VEGF pathway when treated with the humanised recombinant IgG1 monoclonal antibody ramucirumab. In a prospective study, ramucirumab did not improve overall survival in advanced HCC patients receiving sorafenib (OS) any more than a placebo.

7.6 Combination therapy

Cancer researchers are developing ICI-based combination drugs to improve ICI monotherapy response [70]. The 2018 CheckMate067 clinical study [71] found that nivolumab and ipilimumab (a CTLA-4 inhibitor) were superior than monotherapy in advanced melanoma patients.

9. Conclusion

Due to its rapid spread, HCC is typically discovered after chronic liver disease or cirrhosis has progressed. If detected at an early stage, hepatocellular carcinoma can be effectively treated. Proven cancer preventive measures, such as the HPV vaccine, universal blood product screening, safe injection practices, treatment for alcoholics and injectable drug users, and the beginning of antiviral therapy, can help avoid cancers, including HCC. Improvements in both invasive and noninvasive surgical procedures have substantially raised the overall survival rate. The new neo antigenic targeted agent sorafenib has shown encouraging outcomes. Hepatocellular carcinoma is best treated and diagnosed early, thus doctors and nurses should be familiar with the latest techniques. Additional research is required to compare and contrast various biomarkers in order to more accurately evaluate tumour regression and survival.

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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